

Press release ASAP

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Digital and social media literacy project for pre-adolescents promotes positive responsibility and metacognitive approach to skills education: the ASAP project

ASAP project - *A Systemic Approach to social media and pre-adolescents through thinking skills education* - receives funding from the European Union and promotes digital and social media literacy among pre-adolescents. ASAP is a transnational and transdisciplinary project, that includes 5 Countries: Italy, Croatia, Portugal, Slovenia, Czech Republic. It started in September 2022 and will last for 3 years.

The need for a broader approach to digital and social media literacy is relevant considering the ongoing digitisation of the learning and social environment in schools, and outside the school context, boosted also by the recent pandemic. Schools and school parents' associations expressed the urgent need for digital educational interventions. However, most programmes currently implemented in schools are focused on online safety and cyberbullying, often limited to legal and psychological risk prevention, therefore leaving kids (and families) unequipped with the necessary skills to deal with the fast-changing context of social media platforms.

ASAP's main objectives are to promote a broader understanding of the complex phenomenon of digital and social media use – and misuse – among pre-adolescents (11-13), to support the school community – kids, teachers, families – in addressing digital literacy needs through structural, non-contingent approaches and reforms. And to promote the creation of inclusive school contexts that are able to consider the “digital” needs of kids.

As a first step, ASAP is developing a transnational, transdisciplinary study on the relationship between pre-adolescents and social media and its impact on the school community. The project is also modelling an educational programme on digital/social media literacy in the school context, based on a transdisciplinary and metacognitive approach, promoting positive responsibility and a safer proactive digital behaviour.

ASAP will also carry out **4 rounds of digital literacy programme pilots** and **6 co-creation workshops** with project's target groups, which include pre-adolescents, teachers, and families, in each of the partner countries. Additionally, the project will create the profile and training programme and material for the **ASAP Educator**, who will leverage learning-to-learn key competences and metacognition development to increase the digital key competences of the learners. The project will finally produce **key recommendations** for the school community and policymakers based on in-depth analysis of the project experience and findings.

ASAP is **innovative in its approach**, focusing on positive responsibility and learning-to-learn rather than risk prevention. It recognises **pre-adolescence as a specific age in personal development**, which has been a gap in research still essentially unexplored. The project values the kids and their knowledge and digital skills, as well as the mediation role of the digital "illiterate" adults who can help establish a critical and safe relationship with the digital media.

"We are excited to receive funding from the Erasmus+ programme for the ASAP project and are looking forward to promoting and discussing digital and social media skills among pre-adolescents school communities," says the Project Coordinator **Patrizia Giordano**, researcher and project manager at **Fondazione Politecnico di Milano**, "We believe that our innovative approach will create a safer and more responsible digital environment for the school community as whole, and we are excited to work directly with kids, teachers and families to co-create educational resources based on real needs from the school community, and to achieve project goals together."

ASAP has just had **the first co-creation workshop in Maribor**, Slovenia, hosted by one of the project partner, **Doba Business School**. (see pictures attached)

"It has been an intense week of reflections and ideas exchange. A main question led our workshop activities with Slovenian schools representatives and experts: how a reflection on the relation between means and ends is contributing to our understanding of social media?" says Patrizia Giordano.

"We also had the chance to discuss with Slovenian teachers and school principals about how the school community in Slovenia deals with social media use and misuse, and we will compare these inputs with other experiences in partners' countries in the next workshops".

The ASAP Project is a cooperation partnership in School Education, funded under the Erasmus+ programme, agreement number: 2022-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000090043. For more information about the ASAP Project, please visit the project website at www.socialmediakids.eu

Project partners

ASAP project brings together and represents a good range of the experts from Europe in the sector of education and culture, academic research, media and communication, marketing and psychology.

Project leader: Fondazione Politecnico di Milano (FPM) from Italy

Pepita ONLUS from Italy

Associazione Le Nius from Italy

COFAC, Lusófona University from Portugal

DOBA Faculty of Applied Business and Social Studies Maribor (DOBA), from Slovenia

ProEduca z.s. from Czech Republic

Društvo za komunikacijsku i medijsku kulturu (DKMK) - Association for Communication and Media Culture – from Croatia

Istituto Comprensivo Statale (ICS) Via Bologna/Bresso, from Italy

For further information, please contact:

Project communication office: asap@lenius.it

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